

INTRODUCTION

▶ Nanodiamond (ND)

Fig. TEM image of ND.

Core : Diamond crystal

High bulk modulus, High thermal conductivity, High reflective index, High wear resistance

Fig. X-ray diffraction profile of ND.

Shell : Amorphous carbon, Oxygen containing groups

Dispersed at nanoscale in water
Reactive site for chemical modification
Various functionalization

▶ Polyimide (PI)

Super engineering plastic
low processability & poor solubility

▶ Polyamic acid (PAA) ...precursor

Soluble → Processable
High viscosity → Agglomeration

In-situ polymerization

PI/ND nanocomposites @ low ND content

SAMPLE PREPARATION

In-situ polymerization : PAA as well as PI was polymerized under the presence of ND

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Fig. SEM images of the cross section of (A) PI and (B) PI/ND nanocomposites (0.1 wt%).

Fig. UV-vis spectra and optical images of PI and PI/ND nanocomposites.

Fig. X-ray diffraction profiles of PI and PI/ND nanocomposites.

Fig. ATR-FTIR spectra of PI and PI/ND nanocomposites. (A) 2000 cm⁻¹ ~ 400 cm⁻¹ (A) 15300 cm⁻¹ ~ 1490 cm⁻¹.

Fig. Stress-strain curves of PI and PI/ND nanocomposites

Fig. Thermogravimetric traces of PI and PI/ND nanocomposites

Fig. Thermal conductivity of PI and PI/ND nanocomposites

- * High dispersibility
- * Strong interactions
- * High crystallinity
- * Gradient interfacial regions
- * High orientation
- Effective
 - * Stress transfer
 - * Restriction of molecular motions
 - * Conductive pathways

CONCLUSIONS

PI/ND nanocomposites were prepared by *in-situ* polymerization. The homogeneous distribution and high dispersion of ND in PI matrix was achieved. The strong interaction was generated at the interface between PI and ND. The nanocomposites showed significant improvement in the mechanical properties and thermal properties at very low content of ND. In addition, the remarkable increase in thermal conductivity was achieved by the incorporation of ND. The thermal conductivity of the nanocomposites at a content of 0.1 wt% was comparable to that of commercially available thermal interface materials.

Table Young's modulus, tensile strength, elongation at break, toughness and thermal decomposition temperature of PI and PI/ND nanocomposites

ND content (wt%)	Young's modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Toughness (J/g)	Thermal decomposition temperature (°C)
0	4.7	216	12.7	12.1	544
0.01	6.5	265	9.3	11.5	572
0.05	7.5	240	9.0	10.5	578
0.1	7.9	235	7.6	8.2	575

Agglomeration → Stress concentration point → Destruction